

HALOBAN ACTIVE-PASSIVE DIATHESIS: LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY STUDY

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Abstract

This study applies the diathesis theory proposed by Lyon and adopts a qualitative descriptive method where comparative and inductive treatment is carried out on the data collected through a phenomenological approach. The data (Haloban language) used in this study is oral data collected from 2200 informants (native Haloban speakers) who live in two villages, Haloban Village and Asantola Village. Data collection techniques used in this study are listening and note-taking techniques. Then, the data are classified based on the characteristics of language in universal languages empirically. This study shows that the Haloban language has an active-passive diathesis which is one of the important characteristics in the typology of accusative language. In addition to having an active-passive diathesis, the Haloban language also has a medial diathesis. From the perspective of linguistic typology, active and passive diathesis of Haloban language shows a significant difference when compared to active and passive diathesis in accusative language. Haloban has two types of passives: passive ni- and passive pronouns. Based on the marking system, the morphologically marked passive construction ni- has an active form which is also morphologically marked. In passive construction, verbs that indicate passive diathesis are marked by the prefix ni-, while verbs that indicate active diathesis are marked by the prefix {ma-}. Syntactically, the active diathesis subject in the diathesis functions as an adjunct in the form of a prepositional phrase and can be removed. In the construction of passive pronouns, verbs that indicate passive diathesis appear in the form of a base verb, while verbs that indicate active diathesis are marked by the prefix {ma-}. Agents in passive pronoun clauses cannot be omitted. This shows that in passive pronouns, active diathesis is more marked than passive diathesis.

Keywords: Haloban, diathesis, typology, active-passive diathesis.

A. INTRODUCTION

Haloban language is the local language used by the Haloban tribe who inhabit Haloban Island, West Banyak Island District, Singkil Regency, Aceh Province. Geographically, the Haloban people live in two villages called Haloban Village and Asantola Village. Haloban language is one of the local languages in Aceh Province which has not received much attention from both global and Indonesian linguists. As a result, studies on the Haloban language are still very limited. One of the linguistic studies that has not been fully discussed about the Haloban language is the construction of active and passive clauses in the study of linguistic typology. This is one of the objectives of this research. The special aspects of linguistics discussed in this study are active and passive diathesis.

According to Artawa & Purnawati (2020) and Asrul & Daulay (2021) the term diathesis comes from the Greek, which means "state", "setting", or "function". While the term voice comes from Latin which means "tone", or "sound". The term diathesis in English grammar is

commonly called voice, which is one of the subcategories of meaning (meaning categories) that indicate the relationship between participants and the action "Voice indicates the relationship of participants to the action". This relation is morphologically expressed by two contradictory forms, which are later called the active form and the passive form of the verb (Siwi & Ekalestari, 2021; Refnita, 2021; Malchukov, 2019)). Although there is a syntactic relationship, the indication of the voice is also seen in the verbal affix system or other word classes. The so-called voice includes (a) active, if the subject is the actor of the action; (b) passive, when the subject is the object of the action; (c) reflexive, when the subject acts on him; (d) reciprocal, if the plural subject acts in a reciprocal manner; (e) causative, when the actor is exposed to circumstances or events; (f) benefactive, when actors act for others (Shibatani, 2022; Tsuki, 2022; Esteban, 2021).

Accusative-type languages such as English recognize active-passive diathesis and ergative-type languages recognize ergative and anti-passive diathesis. Passive and antipassive diathesis are derived from constructions from the underlying form, namely active and ergative (Birzer, 2019; Akkus, 2022; Oikunomou & Alexiadou, 2022). However, the determination that a language has diathesis or antipassive requires more special study. In general, the languages of the world have a basic strategy for determining their type which is known as active-passive diathesis. According to Fathonah & Romadhon (2021) and Favier et al. (2019), the term voice is understood as a mechanism that selects the main syntactic elements of the subject grammatically from the basic semantic functions of the clause (semantic role). According to Karubaba (2020), the term diathesis is a grammatical category that shows the relationship between the participant or subject and the action expressed by the verb in a clause. In this article, the term diathesis refers to the opinion of Ravhankhodja (2020).

In syntactic typology, Haloban language is a language that has an accusative typology, has an SVO pattern (in a clause with an intransitive predicate and a pronominal subject as a verb and the main subject) and a V (PRO) OS pattern (in a clause with a transitive predicate and a subject other than a pronominal as a verb and a subject). This canonical SVO or V (PRO) OS pattern reflects an active diathesis pattern that places more emphasis on the actor or agent than the patient. Syntactic construction with active diathesis contained in the Haloban language, hereinafter referred to as (BHL) is the basic form. While the syntactic construction with passive diathesis is a derivative construction (derivative form).

In comparison to haloban, several examples of active and passive clauses can be found in Balinese. In Balinese, the construction of a transitive verb clause can be seen as follows:

Actor construction

(1) *Tiang nyepak cicing-e*. [N- kick] (N-form of the verb)

Saya AV.kick dog-DEF

" I kicked the dog"

Undergoer construction:

(2) *Cicing-e sepak tiang.*

[Ø-soccer] (-verb form) dog-DEF UV.

" I kicked the dog."

(Shibatani & Artawa, 2007)

Besides Balinese, Indonesian also has an active clause and a passive clause. Siwi (2021) explains several things in his research on active and passive clauses in Indonesian. They are signifiers that can be formed without agents, markers in with agents of noun phrases, and compound markers. Another research result presented by Katz (2021) is that patients in passive voice construction in Indonesian can have different agents, both preverb and postverbal.

Based on the examples and explanations above, active and passive clauses can be formed from transitive clauses involving subject and object. The subject is the most important grammatical function occupied by a noun or noun phrase (FN) in a clause. In an intransitive clause, the subject is the only core argument contained in the structure. Whereas in the transitive clause, FN is the argument that occupies the highest position in the hierarchy of grammatical functions (Barus & Pujiono, 2021). The object is the main grammatical function along with the subject occupied by the noun or noun phrase which also acts as the main argument. Traditionally, objects are divided into OBJ and OBJ theta (Den, 2019; Jalgasbayevna et al., 2020; Ziegler et al., 2019). In a transitive clause, the object is a function or grammatical relation that must exist and is implied by the predicate (verb). On the other hand, intransitive clauses do not require the existence of an object (Deda, 2020; Hunter, 2018; Mirto, 2021).

In addition to the research on the two languages above, this research is also related to several other studies in diathesis construction. One of them is Siwi's research (2021) entitled Diathesis in Siladang Language. In a study conducted by Siwi (2021), Siladang diathesis has two types of diathesis: active and passive diathesis. The results of the study stated that Siladang language is an accusative language that has a medial diathesis. This study is relevant to this study because it has the same topic about diathesis. The basic difference between the two studies is in the object of the language. Another research relevant to this research is Asrul (2021) entitled Diathesis in South Tapanuli Mandailing Language. In a study conducted by Asrul (2021), Mandailing diathesis has four types of diathesis: active, passive, reflexive, and reciprocal. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative research method. This research has the same object as this research.

The next relevant research is research conducted by Malihah (2018). In a study conducted by Malihah (2018), passive diathesis in Javanese is formed with the marker di-. The Javanese passive diathesis produces the form of "abbreviated agentive passive". This study has relevance to the research conducted by Malihah (2018) because of the similarities in studying passive diathesis. The difference between this study and Malihah's research (2018) is only in the language studied.

B. METHOD

This research is a descriptive-qualitative research that uses a qualitative-phenomenological approach with the aim of making a description, systematic, factual and accurate description of the characters or characteristics possessed by casual workers. As stated by Yogyanti (2022), linguistic research aims to describe language phenomena related to individual languages or universal languages. This research is a field research because the research data is obtained directly from native speakers. The data in this study are in the form of speech. Data are taken from native Haloban speakers. The data collection technique used is recording and recording, meaning that you are free to engage in conversation. Then the elitist technique was used to check the grammatical nature and acceptability of the data. In addition, this study also uses data taken from the results of previous studies. Meanwhile, the data analysis technique used in this research is direct element and vanishing technique. Furthermore, this BHL study aims to describe and explain active-passive diathesis in the study of linguistic typology. Based on the research data and analyzed by linguistic typology, it is stated that BHL is an accusative type language.

There are three things that are considered important in descriptive linguistic research as suggested by Benedetti (2020) are; a) research subjects, b) research objects, and c) research results. Methodologically, the subject of this research is the aspect of casualty called diathesis and its marking, while the object of the research is casual casualty data in the form of a clause and the result is a typological study model. The analysis of BHL diathesis marking in this study uses a linguistic typology approach, especially the concept of typological marking.

There are two types of data used in this article: secondary data from the reference sources of previous researchers and the reference sources listed; the informant is an active BHL speaker, so introspective-intuitive data is also used and this data is displayed without reference. The use of introspective data can be done if the speaker is active in the language studied, namely BHL. This is known as the introspective method of data acquisition (Bischin, 2018; Malchukov, 2022; Bril, 2022).

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The diathesis structure of the Haloban language clause, hereinafter referred to as (BHL), refers to the clause structure in terms of valence, namely the syntactic relationship of the verb and the surrounding elements. Utsumi (2022) suggests that the semantic structure of a clause consists of two main semantic units, namely verbs and nouns. Verbs are the central determinant of the presence of nouns in the semantic structure. Let's observe the center of the verb in the BHL clause.

(3) a. *Awak ayu ayu eda malek.*

Pohon ART tumbang

'The tree fell'.

b. *Mangalek ia awak ayu ayu eda Udin mesa.*

AKT-tumbang-KAU PRO3TG pohon ART Udin sendiri

‘Udin uprooted the tree himself’.

c. *Nilek ia awak ayu ayu eda si Udin.*

PAS-tumbang-KAU PRO3TG pohon ART Udin

‘The tree was uprooted (by) the Udin’.

From the three clauses (3a, b, c) it looks as if the verb forms are different (malek, mangalek, nilek), but actually the basic form of the three forms is one, namely malek which is marked with a mark. The difference in marking results in a change in meaning. The changes in the birth structure are marked by the prefixes {ma-} and {ni-}.

Referring to the explanation, let's observe the following clause which describes construction with active and passive BHL diathesis.

(4) a. *Manganiayo ia panekno eda polisi*

AKT+aniaya PRO3TG pencuri ART Polisi

‘Police molested the thief’

b. *Nianiayo ia polisi panakngo eda*

PAS-aniayo PRO3TG polisi panakngo ART

‘The thief was beaten by the police’.

The example clause (4a,b) describes the syntactic construction of Haloban language which has active and passive diathesis. As explained above, the difference between active-passive diathesis refers to semantic contradictions so that the two examples of clauses are categorized as constructions with active and passive diathesis because the subject of both clauses, namely the police of the perpetrator and influencing the other participant, namely panakngo eda ‘the thief’ . From the two examples of clauses (4a,b) it can be seen that, the active category, if the subject as an active actor is an action that occurs under the control of the subject, the passive category is an action that occurs under the control of the subject, but under the control of another entity outside the subject. i.e. morphological marking on verb.

Verbs in BHL Clause Structure

In a clause structure, a transitive verb is followed by a noun. The number of these nouns can be one or two. Verbs that are followed by one noun are called transitive verbs and verbs that are followed by two nouns are called ditransitive verbs. In contrast to transitive verbs, intransitive verbs are generally followed by non-noun categories (Witzlack & Bickel, 2019; Liubchenko, 2020; Ostman, 2018).

In this article, the term transitive clause is used to name a clause whose verb is filled by a transitive verb. To label a noun which is the valence of a transitive verb, symbols such as A, O, and S are used. If the valence is more than two, the third argument is labeled with the symbol

E. This symbol was adopted from Rosadi (2021). This E symbol can be used for transitive verb arguments to indicate that the verb has an extended transitive or extended intransitive.

Transitive clauses have an important role in the discussion of active-passive diathesis in BHL. BHL transitive clause can be divided into three. First, the Eutransitive Clause, is a clause that has two main arguments, namely A and O. Traditionally, transitive clauses whose verbs are marked by the prefix {ma-} are categorized as active clauses. Let's observe the following clause data:

(5) *Mangareen ia luma-mai (A) mamak (O)*

AKT-perbaiki PRO3TG rumah-1POS paman.

'Uncle repairing our house'.

Second, the ditransitive clause. Verbs in ditransitive clauses are generally marked by the suffix {-kén} or {-i}. However, it should be noted that not all verbs that function as predicates with these two suffixes are dwintransitive verbs. Bitransitive clauses can be divided into two: (a) Dwitransitive with the suffix {-kén}, (b) Dwitransitive with the suffix {-i}. Let's look at the following example of clause (6):

(6) *Mangabekkén anak-ne ia an manok eda*

AKT +bawa+KAU anakPOS3TG PRO3TG makanan burung ART

'The bird brings its young food'.

(7) *Mangeremi achi ia kepeng mamak satiok bulan .*

AKT-kirimi adik PRO3TG uang paman setiap bulan

'Uncle sends brother money every month'.

The verbs in the two clauses above are ditransitive verbs that require three main arguments. The arguments of anak-ne 'the child', an 'food', and manok eda 'the bird' are the main arguments in clause (6) and mamak 'uncle', achi 'sister' and kepeng 'money' are the main arguments in clause (7). While the word ia in the two clauses is not the main argument in that clause and in other active clauses, it is only a pronoun or adverb in place of the Agent argument in the transitive clause. The existence of the word he is mandatory in the BHL system in transitive clauses whose agents are other than pronominals.

In addition to the two-transitive clauses above, it is possible to form another structure if the verb is marked with the suffixes {-kén} and {-i}. The following constructions with {kén} and {-i} suffixes do not include in-transitive clauses. Let's look at the following sample data:

(8) *Ata ek Haloban mamboleikén ool luan mek payo-ne*

orang Pre Haloban AKT-alir-KAU air sungai Pre sawah-POS3TG

'People in Haloban pour river water into their fields'.

(9) *Ata ek Haloban mambolei'i ool luan mek payo-ne*

orang Pre Haloban AKT-alir-APL air sungai Pre sawah-POS3TG

‘People in Haloban pour river water into their fields’.

Third, the alternation of {-kén} and {-i}. Suffixes {-kén and -i} can be attached to the same verb to produce a construction with three arguments in the form of a noun. However, only the verbs with the suffix {-kén} are productive and are included in the bitransitive verb, while the verbs with the suffix {-i} are less productive, in addition, not all verbs with the suffix {-kén} and {-i} can be classified. as a ditransitive verb. Let's look at the following examples of clauses (10a,b):

(10) a. *Mangeremkén ia kepeng (O) mek nenek (E) Delvi (A) satiok bulan*

AKT-kirim PRO3TG uang kepada kakek Delvi setiap bulan

‘Delvi sends money to grandpa every month’.

b. *Mangeremi saweret rambutan (O) ia mek deo (E) Herlin (A) ek walal Ahad*

AKT-kirim satu ikat rambutan PRO3TG kepada saya Herlin Prep hari Minggu

‘Herlin sent me a bunch of rambutan on Sunday’.

In the examples (10a) and (10b), the verb is followed by a noun and a prepositional phrase, so the verb in this example cannot be said to be a ditransitive verb.

Semantically, bitransitive verbs are verbs that require three arguments (A, O and E). Each argument occupies the function of subject, object and complement. Let's look at the argument functions in the following example clause:

(11) *Makhawalikén achi-ne (object) ia karajo (pelengkap) Delvi (subject)*

AKT +cari+KAU adik-POS3TG PRO3TG kerja Delvi

‘Delvi is looking for a job for his sister’.

(12) *Wesang makhawalikén ia karajo (complement) Delvi (subject)*

AKT +cari PRO3TG kerja Delvi

‘Delvi is looking for a job’.

From the example clause (11) above, it can be seen that the object is directly behind the verb and is followed by a complement. In clause (12), the constituent directly behind the verb is the complement and the object in this clause is the implied argument. Complements cannot be removed from the structure. When this complement is committed, it results in an unacceptable clause. Let's look at the following example of clause (13):

(13) **Wesang makhawali achi-ne (O) ia Delvi (S)*

Sedang AKT +cari adikPRO3TG Delvi

‘Delvi is looking for his sister’.

So, only the object in the bitransitive clause can be implied, not the complement. Let's take a look at the following example which is also considered to include a bitransitive clause whose object is implied.

- (14) *Dise mangelak ao bodoh*
dia AKT+ pandang saya bodoh
'He looks at me stupid'.

- (15) *U peker isin Aceh a*
saya mengira dia Aceh orang
'I thought he was Acehnese'

The verb *mangelak* 'looks at' in clause (14) followed by two nouns, *ao* 'me' and *stupid*. The *peker* verb 'to think' in clause (15) is a basic transitive verb without a nasal prefix {*ma-*}. This verb is also followed by two nouns, *isin* 'dia' and *Aceh a* 'people of Aceh'. Each language has a number of verbs that exhibit the same behavior as verbs like this in BHL. Balinese and Riau Malay languages also have structural types such as (14) and (15), as well as English. However, in English, verbs of this type are not classified as bitransitive verbs, but are classified as complex transitive verbs (Barlow, 2019; Chen et al., 2021; Katz, 2021).

Type Diatesis Pasif BHL

Haloban language has two different passive forms, namely 'passive type one' and 'passive type two'. Let's look at the following example clause:

- (16) a. *Mamelli ia wokge sewalu eda opak. (aktif)*
AKT-beli PRO3TG perahu baru ART ayah
'Daddy bought a new boat'.
- b. *Niwelli ia wokge sewalu eda opak. (pasif)*
PAS-beli PRO3TG perahu baru ART ayah
'The new boat was bought by my father'.

The passive rule above shows that the subject is the agent, the verb is indicated by the presence of the prefix *ni-* and the agent in the passive clause is present without the preposition *by*. Because the preposition *by* is not used in the passive rule in the casual casual system. Clause (16b) is called a passive clause. As shown in the example clause (16b), the passive clause is derived from an active clause by changing the object of the active clause into the subject of the passive clause. The subject of the active clause has two kinds of forms. In clause (16a), whether 'father' is an actor or agent is a complement to the passive clause (16b). This kind of passive is called passive form -1 which is formed by a) changing the O (object) in the active clause to S (subject) in the passive clause, b) changing the marker (*ma-*) in the active verb to (*ni-*), and c) S in the active clause becomes oblique (complementary) in the passive clause.

The structure of the active clause and the type of passive clause above can be formulated as follows:

maN-verb + PRO (ia) + object (patient) + subject (actor) (active diathesis)

Ni-verb + PRO (ia) + object (patient) + agent (passive diathesis)

Next, let's look at the following clause:

(17) *Awak eda mayi otong (passive)*

kayu ART kami potong

'We cut the wood'.

In clause (17) above, Demayi 'we' is an actor or agent being part of the predicate of the passive clause. Passive clauses like this are called passive clause-2 in BHL, which especially occurs in the first personal pronouns and second pronouns. The passive-2 clause is formed in a way; a) O in the active clause of crew eda 'kayu itu' which in the active clause is in the position after the verb is moved to the initial position in the passive clause, b) the verb is not marked by the presence of the prefix {ni-}, but appears in its basic form, and c) S which in the active clause functions as an actor or agent turns into a clitic and is placed before the verb and in the passive two, the agent never appears with a preposition. The second type of passive clause has a different word order as shown below:

Subject (patient) + Agent (actor) + verb

Skuka (2020) describes that the meaning of active and passive in a clause involves a verb that is a predicate, subject, object, and the form of the verb used. Verbs in the active clause can be intransitive or transitive verbs and are marked by the presence of an active prefix.

Referring to the opinion of Alwi, et al, passivation in BHL is done in two ways, namely (1) using verbs with {ni-} prefixes and (2) using verbs without prefixes {ni-}. If the symbol S is used for the subject, P for the predicate, and O for the object, the rules for forming passive ni- in BHL are (1) exchanging S with O, and (2) replacing the prefix {ma-} with {ni-} in P, Let's observe the application of this rule in the following example:

(18) *Nisreen he wongge ende (O) mama (S) (passive)*

PAST-fix PRO3TG ART boat Uncle

'The boat was repaired uncle'.

Verbs that function as transitive clause predicates in active construction are generally marked by the prefix ma-, while in passive construction they are marked by the prefix ni-. Clause (18) above is the application of the first form of the passive method. This can be seen in the subject of the clause in the form of a nominal phrase (FN) mamak 'uncle'. If the subject of the active clause in the BHL is a pronoun, then the passive clause is formed using the second passive clause pattern, as shown in the example clause (19) below:

(19) *Payo-ne ngang ise angawan (pasif)*

Kebun-POS3TG sudah dia jual

‘He has sold his garden’

The second passive rule in clause (19) above is formed by; a) move the O to the beginning of the clause, b) remove the prefix {ma-} in P, and c) move the S to the right place before the verb.

Here is the unmarked passive form ni-. This passive is often referred to as a passive pronoun. Verbs in this type of passive are present without a marker. In general, the agents are pronouns, both first, second, and third pronouns. Besides pronouns, kinship nouns can be used deictically as agents of passive clauses.

(20) a. *Deo (S) ngang welli-kén Andi (O) wakdu sewalu (Pel) (aktif)*

ITG sudah beli-KAU Andi baju baru

‘I’ve bought Andi new clothes’.

b. *ngang ao wellikén Andi wakdu sewalu (pasif)*

sudah ITG beli-KAU Andi baju baru

‘Andi I bought new clothes’.

The clause in the example (20a) above is an active transitive clause with the subject argument being a pronoun. Passage of an extra transitive clause does not cause problems because there is only one argument behind the verb, but this is not the case with intransitive clauses, it can cause problems because there are two arguments that come after the verb in its active form. The passive pronoun in (20b) has no problem with its acceptability. This is because the clause only has one object, namely Andi, while the time 'new clothes' in the clause is not an object but functions as a complement (oblique). The choice of the passive form is based on the subject of the active clause. If the subject of the active clause is a third pronoun, there are two choices, namely passive with a marker {ni-} and passive without a marker in the predicate (see example clause 19). If the subject of the active clause is the first and second pronouns, the passive form chosen is the passive form whose verb is not equipped with morphological markers (see example clause 20). If the subject of the active clause is a noun, the selected passive is passive with the marker ni-. However, if the noun is a noun that expresses kinship and is used descriptively, it is okay to choose the passive form with a verb without a marker. From the description above, there are two important aspects that can be seen from a linguistic typology, namely as follows:

- a. There are two passive clauses in BHL: ni-passive and passive whose predicate is present without the marker ni-.
- b. Bitransitive verbs as a category of verbs need to be emphasized as a type of verb in BHL

Accusative type language has active and passive diathesis. Active clauses in accusative language are considered as basic structures, while passive clauses are derived structures.

Typologically, Luraghi et al. (2021) asserted that accusative language has an active and passive diathesis. Active diathesis is an unmarked structure, while passive diathesis is a marked structure. Besides passive *ni-*, BHL also has a passive form whose verb appears without the prefix *ni-*. These are the two main passives in BHL.

Passive Coincidence (accidental) and Ability with Prefix {ta-}

Passive derivation with the prefix {ta-} from the active clause in BHL has the meaning of 'coincidence' or 'accidental' and ability. Basically the prefix {ta-} may be added to transitive verbs that require a general or 'natural' actor. This passive clause with the prefix {ta-} basically does not require the intermediary (actor) to be alive or willing. Therefore, passivation with the prefix {ta-} in BHL has a double meaning, namely; a) a very low level of will/intention from the perpetrator and b) stating the ability of the perpetrator. If the perpetrator is an animate being (has a will, a will), then the actor, who in the passive clause is obliquely related. Let's look at examples of casual clauses with prefix {ta-} derived from basic active clauses (21a) and (21b).

(21) a. *Ulek batik eda taotot mak*

kain batik ART PAS- potong ibu.

'Mother's cut the batik cloth'.

b. *Motor eda tatimpo awak seapok eda*

mobil ART PAS-timpa pohon besar ART

'The car was hit by that big tree'.

(22) a. *Silawe eda tawesei ool angek*

gadis ART PAS-siram air panas

'The girl was scalded'.

b. *Mamak tametet mek bahak bandar.*

Paman PAS-pelanting Pre dalam parit

'Uncle fell into the ditch'.

In the example of clauses (21a and b) above, it appears that the role of the perpetrator Mak 'mother', and the crew of the seapok eda 'the big tree' to take action is very low. The subject which is the only argument of the derived transitive verb (prefixed {ta-}) is affected by the action described by the verb. In BHL there are no known prepositions by the prepositioned FN formers, so the role of the actors emphasizes the meaning of 'coincidence' or 'unintentional'. In clauses (22a and b) the passive with {ta-} where the actor is a general or natural noun describing the role of the actor means 'accidentally' or 'accidentally'.

In addition to meaning 'accidentally' the prefix {ta-} in BHL can also mean the aspect (modality) of 'capable' or 'could be together with passive diathesis. If the meaning of the aspect of 'able' or 'can' is included, then the level of 'willingness' or 'intentional' of the perpetrator becomes high. In this case, the perpetrator is usually an animate being or a general noun who

is considered to have a will and intention. Actors are marked by the preposition *oak* (without meaning) (obliquely related). In this type of construction the preposition *ek* tends to be preserved, which indicates the intentional meaning of the actor. Let's look at the example in clause (23) below:

(23) *Talawan ek Herlin woya eda*
terlawan Pre Herlin buaya ART

'Herlin can also fight the crocodile'.

Passive derivation with prefix {*ta-*} from the active clause in BHL has the meaning of 'intentional' and 'ability'. Furthermore, the decrease in the passive meaning of the active clause shows that BHL has the characteristics of language as an accusative language. The following sections will discuss BHL medial diathesis.

BHL Medial Diathesis

A medial diathesis is a reflexive diathesis, that is, a diathesis that is influenced by one's own actions. Based on the syntactic-semantic behavior of the world's languages, the grammatical features of medial diathesis have the meanings of (1) reflexive activity, and (2) reciprocal. This diathesis shows a dual status, namely as a source of action and as a being who is influenced or a place of influence of action, or reveals the character of the subject and the consequences that arise, good or bad, are directed to the subject. Let's observe some verbal constructions with the following BHL medial diathesis:

(24) *Wereng manyase ia wangone Mak.*
sedang AKT-cuci PRO3TG mukaPOS3TG Ibu
'Mom is washing her face'

(25) *pak Atar wteng mararang.*
Pak Atar sedang berdiang
'Mr. Atar is warming up'.

(26) *Chabarne rui' sengkkel nga anak SD senga manggantung wangkene.*
kabarnya Pre Singkil ada anak SD gantung diri.
'It is said that in Singkil there is an elementary school child who hanged himself'.

The prefix {*ma-*} in the example clause (24) above is a marker of the medial diathesis in reflexive construction. In clauses (25, and 26) it is a verbal construction with medial diathesis which shows the dual status of the subject in the clause, namely; as a source of action and as a being who is influenced (gets the effect of the verb), the subject (agent) carries out activities that affect or affect himself. In addition to reflexive constructions, BHL also contains the affix {*mesi-*} which has the meaning of 'mutual' (reciprocal). Let's look at an example of a reciprocally constructed medial diathesis:

(27) *Jokowi alek ata –ata ek kampong Haloban mesiseba.*

Jokowi CONJ orang-orang Pre kampung Haloban PREF-salaman.

‘Jokowi and the people in Haloban village shake hands with each other’.

(28) *Rita alek achi-ne mesisayang*

Rita CONJ adik-POS3TG PREF-sayang

‘Rita and her sister love each other’

Clauses (27) and (28) above are semantically the same structure. In the examples of clauses (27) and (28) morphological markers for verbal constructions with medial diathesis indicate reciprocal meanings. Next, let's look at verbal clauses with medial diathesis whose verbs are marked with zero and marked with {basi-}.

(29) a. *pak Atar rarang ek luma- mai*

pak Atar berdiang Pre rumah POS1JM

‘Mr. Atar is warm in our house’.

b. *Pak Atar alek makne wteng basirarang.*

pak Atar CONJ ibuPOS3TG sedang PREF berdiang

‘Mr. Atar and his mother are warm to each other’.

Example (29a) is a medial diathesis verbal construction marked with a reflexive construction and clause (29b) is a zero-marked medial diathesis verbal construction marked {basi-}.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that morphologically medial diathesis can be marked by prefix (ma-), prefix zero, prefix {basi-}, and prefix {mesi-}. These affixes have various grammatical functions and semantic roles. The determination of the semantic roles of the affixes above depends on the semantic content of the verb they mark and the pragmatic functions of the clause in question (Legate et al., 2020; Katz, 2021). Furthermore, it can be concluded that BHL as an accusative language has grammatical behavior that can be categorized as a language that has active, passive, and medial diathesis (Noorlander, 2021; Zuniga & Kittila, 2019).

Regarding passive diathesis in BHL, it can be said that the syntactic construction with passive diathesis is a derivative construction. Finally, it can be concluded that the characteristics of passive construction in BHL consist of (1) the subject of the passive clause is the direct object of the corresponding active clause (2) the FN object (O) of origin becomes S passive clause (3) FN agent (A) enters the function peripheral, marked by non-core cases, prepositions, and so on; The FN can be deleted although there is always the option to include it.

D. CONCLUSION

The different views on active and passive diathesis with morphological and syntactic characteristics seem to stem from two things, namely the type of language being analyzed and the theoretical approach used. This study shows that the Haloban language has an active-passive diathesis which is one of the important characteristics in the typology of accusative language. In addition to having an active-passive diathesis, Haloban languages also have a medial diathesis. From the perspective of linguistic typology, BHL's active and passive diathesis shows a significant difference when compared to active and passive diathesis in accusative type languages. BHL has two types of passives: passive ni- and passive pronouns. This passive is compared to its active form based on the marking system, both active and passive diathesis have morphological markings. Active diathesis has a verb marked ma-, while the verb in the passive diathesis is marked ni- and syntactically the subject of the active clause functions as an adjunct in the form of a prepositional phrase and can be erased. When viewed from the contingency system, verbs in passive pronouns are in the form of basic verbs, while active verbs are marked by prefix {ma-} and agents in passive pronoun clauses cannot be removed. This shows that active diathesis is more marked than the so-called pronoun passive diathesis.

Based on observations and analysis of markings, BHL diathesis is analyzed as a language that has active and passive diathesis, however, this diathesis is not seen critically from a typological perspective. The basic assumption of linguistic typology related to diathesis is that the active clause is an unmarked base clause and the passive clause is a marked derived clause. Thus, the novelty of the results of this analysis is to clarify that the active and passive diathesis analysis developed for casual workers is not in accordance with the rules of linguistic typology marking.

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